

PRINCIPLES OF PUBLIC CIVIL SERVICE

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Abstract

The article analyzes the core principles of public civil service enshrined in the legislation of the Republic of Uzbekistan. These principles define the main directions of public administration and outline the obligations of state bodies and officials toward society and citizens. The critique highlights the general nature of the principles articulated in the legislation and the lack of detailed elaboration. Additionally, the article examines the principles outlined in the draft code of ethics for public servants, providing descriptions, legislative requirements, and practical implementation. Attention is drawn to existing issues in the recruitment process and the absence of criteria for assessing the moral and ethical qualities of candidates. The article underscores the relevance of studying the principles of public service and their application in practice.

Keywords: public civil service, principles of public service, legislation, code of ethics, legality, fairness, intolerance to corruption.

It is well known that principles are fundamental guidelines and ideas that pertain to the activities of all civil services and play a guiding role. The state civil service is organized based on specific principles enshrined in legislative acts.

The essence of the principles of the state civil service is embedded in its role as a fundamental category of public administration. The principles governing the performance of state civil service duties are directly linked to the general principles of public service. According to Article 5 of the Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On State Civil Service," the main principles of the state civil service include:

Unity and stability of the state civil service system;

Legality;

Fairness;

Service to the people;

Accountability of state bodies and officials to society and citizens;

Priority of human rights, freedoms, and legitimate interests;

Openness and transparency;

Impartiality, professionalism, and competence;

Equal rights for citizens of the Republic of Uzbekistan in entering the state civil service;

Legal and social protection of state civil servants.

It should be noted that although the principles of the state civil service are defined in legislation, their descriptions are not provided. This can lead to varying interpretations of these principles.

The draft Code of Ethics for State Servants of the Republic of Uzbekistan stipulates that state servants should carry out their professional activities based on legality, fairness, prioritization of citizens' rights, freedoms, and legitimate interests, patriotism and dedication to their duty, loyalty to the interests of the state and society, honesty, impartiality, openness, intolerance of corruption, professionalism, competence, efficiency, and frugality. The draft provides descriptions for each principle.

For instance, the principle of legality requires state servants to strictly comply with the Constitution of the Republic of Uzbekistan and other legislative acts and to fulfill their requirements.

Under the principle of fairness, it is stipulated that a public servant must fulfill their duties fairly, promptly, conscientiously, and with a high level of professionalism. Discrimination or the application of criteria such as social, racial, national, religious, or other similar factors is not permitted in the performance of public service duties.

The principle of prioritizing citizens' rights, freedoms, and legitimate interests requires public servants to avoid violations of these rights, freedoms, and interests, and to contribute to their restoration if they are infringed.

Under the principle of patriotism and dedication to duty, public servants are expected to conduct their activities based on high patriotism, dedication to their service duties, and other ethical virtues. Public servants must perform their responsibilities and duties irrespective of personal interests, ideological, or religious views.

The principle of loyalty to the interests of citizens, society, and the state mandates that public organization employees perform their official duties conscientiously, giving precedence to the interests of citizens, society, and the state, and abstaining from any actions influenced by personal interests.

The principle of integrity is reflected in a public servant's honest fulfillment of their duties, truthfulness, and abstention from inappropriate actions. Public servants are required to remain impartial, avoid conflicts of interest or undue

influence from others, and refrain from any actions that may negatively impact the reputation of the public organization.

The principle of impartiality stipulates that public servants must not favor or give preferential treatment to any individuals, groups, or organizations while performing their duties. They must remain independent of such influences, respect the rights, obligations, and legitimate interests of citizens, and prevent any instances of discrimination.

Under the principle of openness, it is required that public organizations publish information regarding compliance with ethical standards by public servants on their official websites, provided that such information does not constitute state secrets or other confidential information protected by law.

The principle of intolerance toward corruption mandates that public servants adopt an uncompromising stance against all forms of corruption, actively fight against it, and contribute to its prevention.

Public servants are obligated to inform their superiors or law enforcement authorities of any instances where they are approached by individuals attempting to involve them in corruption-related offenses, as well as any facts of similar offenses committed by other employees of the public organization that come to their attention.

The principle of professionalism and competence requires public servants to maintain an impeccable professional reputation, foster a healthy moral and psychological environment within their team, and continuously enhance the knowledge and skills necessary for effectively fulfilling their duties.

Under the principles of efficiency and cost-effectiveness, public servants are required to perform their duties efficiently in accordance with legislative acts and the internal rules and regulations of their organization. They must handle entrusted property and financial resources with care and frugality.

It should be noted that the "Unified Open Portal of Vacancies for Public Civil Servants" (<https://vacancy.argos.uz/>) has been developed to ensure that vacant positions in public civil service are filled by suitable candidates through an open and independent selection process. To date, nearly 10,000 candidates have participated in competitions for various public service positions through this system. Approximately 5,000 of the most qualified candidates have been employed in public service.

The selection process involves three stages, successfully completing which ensures that the most suitable specialists fill the available vacancies. However, it has been observed that criteria for assessing the moral, ethical, and patriotic

qualities of future public civil servants, as well as clear and principled rules for performing duties, have not yet been developed. This highlights the importance of studying the principles of serving in public civil service.

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